

Coordination Polymers of the Schiff's Base Derived from Oxalyl Dihydrazide and Diacetyl

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Oxalyl-dihydrazide has been condensed with diacetyl to give a polymeric Schiff's base which has been shown to be a pentamer with acetyl end-groups. The presence of acetyl end-groups has been demonstrated by the reaction of the Schiff's base with methyl amine. Metallic ions like Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} have been incorporated into the polymeric Schiff's base and the structures and the thermal stability of the resultant complexes have been discussed.

The coordination polymers form a promising group of compounds which have come under investigation only recently. Schiff's bases and related azo-methines have attracted the attention of the investigators as very useful catenating ligands since long; one particularly interesting outcome of these investigations being the synthesis of several polymeric Schiff's bases which have been utilised in making coordination polymers through metallization of the preformed organic polymers containing suitably spaced donor atoms. Marvel and Torkoy¹ prepared polymers by the reaction of bis-salicylaldehydes and *o*-phenylene diamine and metallized these with Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , and Cd^{2+} . Goodwin and Bailar² have extended the work of Marvel and Torkoy to six-coordinate metal ions by using tri- and tetramines, in place of *o*-phenylene diamine.

The present study was undertaken with a view to explore the possibility of synthesising polymeric ligands through the condensation of aliphatic dicarboxy-dihydrazides with α -diketones, such as diacetyl and also of incorporating metallic ions into the preformed polymeric organic ligands.

The present paper describes the synthesis of the polymeric Schiff's base obtained from the condensation of oxalyl-dihydrazide and diacetyl and preparation of the metal-chelates of this Schiff's base with metallic ions like Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} .

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Schiff's base : Oxalyl dihydrazide (11.8 g) and diacetyl (9 g.) were refluxed in aqueous alcohol. After about 30 min. a light yellow solid formed. The reflux was continued for an additional 1 hr and the reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature. The precipitated product was collected on a filter washed with aqueous alcohol and dried in a desiccator. The light yellow compound is insoluble in common solvents like acetone, benzene, chloroform, very slightly soluble in hot alcohol, but completely soluble in hot dil. ammonia. Calc. for $\text{OH}_3\text{C}_2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_2\text{N}_4]_5\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}$. N, 30.2%; C, 44.06%; H, 4.96%. Found : N, 30.3%; C, 43.82%; H, 4.52%.

1. C. S. Marvel and N. Torkoy, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 6000.

2. H. A. Goodwin and J. C. Bailar, Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2467.

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Presence of acetyl end-groups of the polymeric Schiff's base : Formation of methyl-imine derivative : To a suspension of the Schiff's base in alcohol, an aqueous solution of methyl-amine was added dropwise until a clear yellow solution was obtained. The resultant solution was refluxed on the water-bath for an hour and then concentrated to a small volume on water-bath. On cooling a yellow solid separated out. This was filtered, washed repeatedly with water and then dried in a desiccator.

The substance forms yellow powder which is insoluble in water, but sparingly soluble in hot benzene and alcohol. Calc. for $\text{CH}_3\text{C}=\text{NCH}_3[\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N}_4]_5\text{H}_3\text{C.N}=\text{C.CH}_3$. N, 32.36%; C, 45.37%; H, 5.46%. Found : N, 32.17%; C, 45.03%; H, 5.22%.

Preparation of the metal chelates of the polymeric Schiff's base : To a suspension of the ligand (1 m. mole) in alcohol, aqueous ammonia was added dropwise while heating on the water bath until a clear yellow solution was obtained. To this hot yellow solution was added an alcoholic solution of metal acetate hydrate (5 m. mole). When the metal solution was added to the solution containing the ligand, there was a sudden change in the colour of the solution, often accompanied by slight precipitation [in the case of Cu(II) and Cd(II)]. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. and in every case, during reflux a coloured compound separated out which remained dispersed throughout the solution. After reflux, the reaction mixture was concentrated to a small volume on the water bath and then refrigerated overnight. The solid product, thus settled, was collected by filtration, washed with water and alcohol and then dried in a desiccator.

Colours of the metal chelate polymers :

Cu (II)	:	Deep brown
Ni (II)	:	Bright red
Zn (II)	:	Light yellow
Cd (II)	:	Orange yellow

Analyses of the metallic chelates : Analyses of nitrogen and the metal in the polymer were done by usual methods. Water was estimated by loss in weight at 120–125°. Results of analyses are given in Table I.

TABLE I
Analytical data for the metal-chelates

Composition	Calculated (%)			Found (%)		
	N	M	Water	N	M	Water
$\text{OH}_3\text{C}_2[\text{L Cu.2H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}$	19.81	22.48	12.73	20.15	22.30	12.99
$\text{OH}_3\text{C}_2[\text{L Ni.2H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}$	20.16	21.13	12.95	19.86	21.21	12.60
$\text{OH}_3\text{C}_2[\text{L Zn.2H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}$	19.67	22.98	12.65	19.50	22.72	12.30
$\text{OH}_3\text{C}_2[\text{L Cd.2H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}$	16.89	33.89	10.85	16.63	33.79	10.68

Solubility data : All the polymeric chelates are insoluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, benzene, but only slightly soluble in boiling dimethyl formamide. They are appreciably soluble in dil. alkali, but the alkaline solutions gradually decomposed.

Thermal decomposition of the metal-chelate polymers : Thermal decomposition studies were made on all the compounds by heating samples (about 100 mg) at various temperatures in a furnace starting from 100°. The temperature was allowed to increase by 25° gaps and the compounds were kept at any particular temperature for a period of 2 hrs and then after cooling in a desiccator, were weighed to determine the loss in weight of the sample. Heating was continued in this manner till the sample showed signs of decomposition which was evident from an abrupt large loss in the weight. Results of observations are shown in Table II, tabulated as the percent weight-loss of the compounds at different temperatures. The weight-loss percentages were plotted against temperatures in each case and the respective thermal decomposition curve was thus obtained (Fig. I and II).

FIG. 1. THERMAL DECOMPOSITION CURVES OF
(A) COPPER-OXALYL DIHYDRAZIDE - DIACETYL
(B) NICKEL-OXALYL DIHYDRAZIDE - DIACETYL

FIG. II. THERMAL DECOMPOSITION CURVES OF
 (A) ZINC - OXALYL DIHYDRAZIDE - DIACETYL
 (B) CADMIUM - OXALYL DIHYDRAZIDE - DIACETYL

TABLE II

Percentage weight loss of oxalyl-dihydrazide-diacetyl metal complexes

Temp. in °C	Copper(II)	Nickel(II)	Zinc(II)	Cadmium(II)
100	10.55	11.05	9.06	9.50
125	13.05	12.80	12.25	10.90
150	18.06	17.31	12.90	12.88
175	20.50	20.43	12.95	14.49
200	25.60	22.93	13.06	14.85
225	26.62	24.04	13.62	15.03
250	28.23	25.32	13.73	15.92
275	31.52(*)	27.24(*)	14.15	18.23
300	57.50	53.50	15.05(*)	25.23(*)
325	—	—	42.15	48.62

* The compound starts decomposition after this point.

DISCUSSION

The Schiff's base formed by the condensation of oxalyl-dihydrazide and diacetyl is shown to be a pentamer with acetyl end-groups ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$) and is assigned the following

structure (A) which is capable in existing in tautomeric form (B) :

(A)

(B)

The presence of acetyl end-groups has been demonstrated by the reaction of (A) with methylamine whereby the corresponding methyl-imine (C) has been formed :

(C)

The Schiff's base (A) reacts with the acetate salt of bivalent metals like Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II) in aqueous ammoniacal alcohol media giving highly coloured compounds. From elemental analyses, the metal-chelates closely agree with the general empirical formulation : $\text{H}_3\text{C}\cdot\text{OC}[\text{LM}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]_5\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_3$ where M = Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) and LH_2 represents a unit of the condensation product (A or B). Agreement between the calculated and the observed values in the elemental analyses have been greatly improved by assuming two water molecules to be associated per metal atom. This assumption is reasonable since metal atoms are present in the polymer chain and water of crystallisation is possible; moreover, the maximum coordination number of the metals concerned is six. Evaluation of the water contents of these compounds supports this assumption. The compounds may be

considered as the metal-chelates of the preformed polymeric Schiff's base reacting in its enolic form³ (B) and the following structure (D) appears highly probable for them :

The extreme insolubility of all the metal-chelates in common organic solvents like alcohol, acetone, chloroform and benzene points to their polymeric structures proposed.

Thermal stability studies of the polymeric metal-chelates upto the onset of decomposition point indicate that they are thermally quite stable and the temperatures at which the compounds start decomposition range from 300–325°. The weight-loss percentages at different temperatures for the metal-chelates reveal the following facts :

(a) The weight-loss percentage at temperature between 120–125° corresponds closely to the water content of the metal-chelates.

(b) Zinc (II) compound is thermally the most stable one as shown by the minimum weight-loss before decomposition, while the copper(II) compound is thermally the least stable. The latter observation is in conformity with the theoretical prediction that Zn(II) complexes with completely filled 3d orbitals of the central metal ion should be more stable than the corresponding Cu(II) complexes.

In the thermal decomposition curves drawn by plotting weight-loss percentages against temperatures, the initial slopes probably represent the volatilisation of water molecules associated with the metal-atom in the polymer; thus the Zinc(II) polymer, lost approx. 12% of its weight prior to the sharp break in the curve and this value agrees closely with the calculated 12.6% water content in the polymeric molecule, $H_3C.CO[ZnL.2H_2O]_5.CO.CH_3$. After this initial weight-loss, a rather sharp-break occurred in each of the curves signifying the onset of a decomposition process.

Although the exact molecular weights of these-metal chelate polymers could not be ascertained for lack of their solubility in common organic solvents, the geometry of the ligand molecule, the extreme insolubility of the compounds, their characteristic colours and great thermal stability seem to suggest that they are the metal-chelates of the preformed polymeric Schiff's base.

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